

Association of Nosocomial Burns and Bacterial Colonization in Iraqi Patients

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Abstract:

Burn injury is a prevalent and severe form of trauma, posing a significant global public health concern. This study included isolating causative agents involved in nosocomial burns in Iraqi patients. 65 swabs from burn wounds were collected aseptically from a specialty hospital in Baghdad city. The swabs were cultured on routinely used culture media prepared in the laboratory and diagnosed using conventional biochemical tests, and the VITEK-2 compact system validated their findings. The findings revealed that 47 (72.3%) isolates had growth, and the remaining 27.7% of the swabs did not

grow. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was the predominant species bacteria isolated in percent (43%), followed by *Staphylococcus aureus* in percent (26%), *Corynebacterium spp.* (11%), *Proteus vulgaris* (6%), whereas "*Escherichia coli*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, and *Serratia marcescens*" isolated in similar percent (4%), and *Klebsiella spp.* in the lowest percent (2%). Moreover, antibiotic susceptibility testing was also done using VITEK-2 compact system against Amoxiclav, Ticarcillin, Ceftriaxone, Imipenem, Gentamicin, Amikacin, Tetracycline, Doxycycline, Ciprofloxacin, and Erythromycin.

Keywords: Burn wounds, nosocomial infections, Culture, Antibiotic Resistance.

Introduction

Burn injury is considered a prevalent and severe form of trauma, and a major public health issue worldwide (Church et al., 2006). Burned patients may still get life-threatening infections, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is a significant nosocomial pathogen that significantly contributes to these infections. The most susceptible site for opportunistic colonization of organisms is a burn wound; the skin barrier which represents

the defense against invasion by microorganisms is destroyed by thermal injury. This site is the most common cause of sepsis in these patients (Mooney and Gamelli, 1989).

The surfaces of burn wounds remain sterile after thermal injury but eventually become colonized with microorganisms (Monafo and Freedman, 1987), some gram-positive bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* survive the thermal injury are found deeply within hair follicles and sweat

glands, and are heavily found within the first 48 hours on the surface of the burn wound. Most often, burn infections result in mortality and morbidity among hospitalized burn patients (McManus, 1994), in patients with burns across more than 40% of their body surface area, 75% die following thermal injuries and are associated with infections (Vindences and Bjercknes, 1995). Burn patients have a greater mortality rate because of factors including their immunocompromised status (Pruitt, 1998), age, burn injury, depth, and microbial factors like toxin and enzyme production, type and number of colonizing organisms, and systemic dissemination (Pruitt and McManus, 1984). Bacteria invade exposed wounds after burn injuries. These bacteria develop from the patient's endogenous cutaneous, respiratory, and gastrointestinal flora (Barret and Herndon, 2003). Direct contact with external environmental surfaces, air, fomites, unclean hands of healthcare personnel, and water may introduce microorganisms onto a patient's skin (Weber et al., 1997). Gram-negative bacteria from the patient's gastrointestinal flora colonize it after a few days of injury (Manson, et al., 1992), while broad-spectrum antibiotic treatment delays the colonization of fungi and yeasts (Burdge et al., 1988). Nosocomial pathogens are typically more antibiotic resistant than those from the patient's own normal flora (Clark et al., 2003). Most commonly isolated pathogen in burn wound infections was group A beta-hemolytic streptococci (*Streptococcus pyogenes*) (Bang et al., 1999). Then *Staphylococcus aureus* (Lilly et al., 1979), and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* from an environmental source of endogenous gastrointestinal flora are the most frequent in many burn wound sites (Altoparlak et al., 2004). "Gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, viruses, and fungi" are examples of less common microorganisms that have progressively expanded over the previous decade. Anaerobic bacteria infections can occur as a result of exposed wound dressings rather than occlusive dressings or electrical burns (Murray and Finegold, 1984).

This study aims to investigate the relationship between bacterial species' colonization of

nosocomial burns and their antimicrobial resistance patterns in burn units of Iraq to assess control and preventive strategies and lower the rates of death.

Materials and Methods

Sixty-five burn wounds swabs were collected from patients admitted to Burn Hospital in Baghdad, Iraq. These swabs were inoculated on Blood agar and MacConkey agar, next the resultant cultures were identified by conventional biochemical tests validated by VITEK-2 compact system (Collee et al., 1996). Antibiotic susceptibility test of the isolates were performed using commercial VITEK-2 kit against a few antibiotics including "Amoxiclav (AMC) 30 µg, Ticarcillin (TIC) 75 µg, Ceftriaxone (CRO) 30 µg, Imipenem (IMP) 10 µg, Gentamicin (CN) 10 µg, Amikacin (AK) 30 µg, Doxycycline (DO) 30 µg, Tetracycline (TE) 30 µg, Ciprofloxacin (CIP) 5 µg, and Erythromycin (E) 30 µg".

Results and Discussion

A total of (65) burn swabs, the results indicated that 47 samples (72.3%) showed positive culture (bacterial isolates), while 18 samples (27.7%) showed negative culture (no growth) (see Table 1).

Table 1. Distribution of Burn Wounds Swabs Based on The Type of Bacterial Culture Result

Type of Results	No. of Samples	Percentage (%)
Positive culture	47	72.3
Negative culture	18	27.7
Total	65	100

It was also found that, as Figure 1 illustrates, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* represented 43% of all bacteria isolated. This was followed by *Staphylococcus aureus* in percent (26%), *Corynebacterium spp.* (11%), *Proteus vulgaris* (6%), whereas "*Escherichia coli*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, and

Serratia marcescens" isolated in similar percent (4%), and *Klebsiella spp.* in the lowest percent (2%).

Figure 1. The Percentage of Causative Pathogenic Bacteria Involved in Nosocomial Burn Infections

As indicated in Table 2, the VITEK-2 compact system was utilized to assess each isolate's susceptibility to Amoxiclav (AMC), Ticarcillin (TIC), Ceftriaxone (CRO), Imipenem (IMP),

Gentamicin (GN), Amikacin (AK), Tetracycline (TE), Doxycycline (DO), Ciprofloxacin (CIP), and Erythromycin (ERY).

Table 2. Antibiotic Susceptibility of All Bacterial Isolates in Patients with Burn Wound Infection

Organism	AMC	CIP	IMP	CRO	AK	TIC	TE	ERY	DO	GN
<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	100%	55%	40%	60%	48%	80%	91%	88%	95%	73%
<i>S. aureus</i>	90%	56%	45%	65%	98%	100%	58%	60%	75%	70%
<i>Corynebacterium spp.</i>	45%	0	25%	0	0	30%	7%	0	5%	2%
<i>P. vulgaris</i>	100%	0	98%	0	0	100%	88%	75%	90%	60%
<i>E. coli</i>	95%	0	100%	0	0	98%	60%	68%	74%	71%
<i>E. faecalis</i>	3%	0	100%	0	100%	100%	95%	90%	98%	95%
<i>S. marcescens</i>	100%	0	95%	0	0	100%	20%	7%	15%	10%
<i>Klebsiella spp.</i>	87%	42%	96%	35%	48%	87%	68%	77%	72%	63%

The findings of this study are exemplified by the following: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* displayed 100% resistance to Amoxiclav, 55% resistance to Ciprofloxacin, 40% resistance to Imipenem, 60% resistance to Ceftriaxone, 48 resistance to Amikacin, 80% resistance to Ticarcillin, 91% resistance to Tetracycline, 88% resistance to

Erythromycin and 95% resistance to Doxycycline, and 73% resistance to Gentamicin. Conversely, *Staphylococcus aureus* showed 100% Amoxiclav resistance, 56% Ciprofloxacin resistance, 45% Imipenem resistance, 65% Ceftriaxone resistance, 98% Amikacin resistance, 100% Ticarcillin resistance, 58%

Tetracycline resistance, 60% Erythromycin resistance, 75% Doxycycline resistance and 70% Gentamicin resistance. *Corynebacterium spp.* demonstrated resistance to Imipenem by 45%, to Amoxiclav by 25%, to Ticarcillin by 30%, to Tetracycline by 7%, to Doxycycline by 5%, and Gentamicin by 2%, while *Proteus vulgaris* exhibited resistance to Amoxiclav by 100%, to Ticarcillin by 100%, and to Tetracycline by 88%, with resistance to Imipenem by 98%, to Doxycycline by 90% and to Gentamicin by 60%, and to Erythromycin by 75%. The remaining bacterial resistance rates are detailed in Table 2.

Nosocomial infections are often a risk factor for people with burns in addition to additional factors, such as the type of microbes existing in the burn wound site, the burn injury itself, and the development of sepsis. These factors can lead to significant complications and mortality. The usage of therapeutic and medical interventions, in combination with an extended length of stay in the hospital can elevate the bacterial load of the wound and wound infections (Tchakal-Mesbahi, et al., 2021; Oncul et al., 2009; Kumar et al., 2011).

Nevertheless, the control and prevention of these infections can be challenging because of the breakdown of the skin barrier and the potential for acquiring resistant organisms in the burn unit environment. These resistant pathogens can easily pass from one patient to another (Tredget et al., 2004; Qader and Muhamed, 2010). Over extended courses of antibiotics, we isolated three multidrug resistant strains "*P. aeruginosa*, *A. baumannii*, and *S. aureus*" (Azimi et al., 2011; Bayat et al., 2003).

In the past ten years, extended-spectrum beta-lactamase producing Enterobacteriaceae may be identified from burns in the background of common use of these pathogens in general of 3rd generation cephalosporins (Tredget et al., 2004). The contamination in burns may reflect a colonization from the patients gastrointestinal flora, most likely from the perineum, or environmental organisms & missed cutaneous organisms. Based on this information, the screen for these types of bacteria could be useful to assist with the development of an empiric

antibiotic regimen to address the types of pathogens. The practicality of this is uncertain due to cost, percent of previously mentioned resistance and lack of central data source for resistance trends (Tredget et al., 2004; Zorgani et al., 2010). In a study carried out in Algeria, reporting the most predominant Gram negative burn isolates from swabs and carts were *P. aeruginosa* 33.91%, *Klebsiella* species 25.14%, *Acinetobacter baumannii* 16.37%, *Proteus mirabilis* 9.94%, *Escherichia coli* 8.18%, *Enterobacter* species 4.67%, *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* 1.16% and *Citrobacter freundii* 0.58%. All the *S. aureus* isolates identified were extremely resistant to the majority of the antibiotics tested, such as penicillin 100%, and at least 80% resistance to Trimethoprim+Sulfamethazole, ciprofloxacin and gentamicin. The *Pseudomonas* isolates were very resistant greater than 60% to cefotaxime, ceftazidime for *psuedomonas*, imipenem and moderate resistance to Ciprofloxacin (50%) and less resistance to amikacin (29.31%) the best *Pseudomonas* susceptibilities observed to colistin. The 37 *P. aeruginosa* isolates had 64% of the isolates were multiple drug resistant. The *K. pneumoniae* isolates were very high more than 80% cefotaxime, cephalexin, gentamicin and amikacin were moderate for ciprofloxacin (53.48%). In the study performed by Hassuna et al., of burn patients in Egypt, many MDR isolates of the gram-negative bacteria *A. baumannii* and *P. aeruginosa* existed. The resistant isolates in the Hassuna study was associated with a higher patient mortality rate (Tchakal-Mesbahi et al., 2021). "The pattern of bacterial resistance is essential for epidemiological and medical reasons" and the finding of antibiograms presented potential future alarming concerns as the main bacteria were significantly resistant to commonly available antimicrobials. Immediately after burn injury, the burn wounds are sterile; however, within 48 hours they become colonized with gram-positive bacteria [Alwan et al., 2011; Embil et al., 2001]. Local wound management is crucial for prevention of desiccation of viable tissue and control of bacteria. To protect the full thickness and partial-thickness of a soft burn wound, a closed dressing is mandatory until early excision of the burn wound and grafting which is the standard

of care in areas where resources are available (Alwan et al., 2011). In contrast, In 2008, another study carried out at Al-Kindy Hospital, Baghdad, Iraq, showed that 25 samples (35.7%) that were clear of bacterial growth, while 45 wound swabs (64.3%) showed bacterial isolates. *P. aeruginosa* was the most predominant isolate with a percentage of 48.9%, followed by *S. aureus* with a percentage of 24.4%, and *Citrobacter* 13.3%. "*Enterobacter* spp. and coagulase-negative *Staphylococci* were each 5 isolates (11.1 %), *P. vulgaris*, *Corynebacterium* spp. and *Micrococcus* spp. were each 3 isolates (6.66%), *P. mirabilis*, *E. faecalis*, *E. coli* and *Streptococcus* spp. were each 2 isolates (4.44%). *Klebsiella* spp., *Bacillus* spp., *S. marcescens* and *S. rubidia* were each only 2.22% of the cases (one isolate each)" (Alwan et al., 2011). Moreover, it was shown that there was only moderately resistance for *P. aeruginosa* to ciprofloxacin (54.17%) and amikacin (45.83%) whereas as significantly higher resistance for doxycycline (73.33%), oxytetracycline (69.57%) and ticarcilin (68.75%), and gentamicin (63.64%). Further, *Staphylococcus aureus* exhibited complete resistance (100%) to amikacin, ticarcillin, and gentamicin, and for doxycycline (75.70%), oxacillin (81.81%) and oxytetracycline (85.71%) *E. coli* (41.66%) and chloramphenicol (28.57%) had the lower resistance. Accordingly, *E. faecalis* was 100% responsive to both ciprofloxacin and chloramphenicol, however, it was resistant to all other antimicrobials. *Klebsiella* spp., however, was resistant 100% to all antimicrobials tested. While 50% of *Enterobacter* spp. was resistant to the majority of antimicrobials, 50% of *Enterobacter* spp. was responsive to ciprofloxacin, doxycycline, and oxytetracycline. In addition, *P. vulgaris* exhibited resistance to four antibiotics and a reduced level of resistance (33.3%) to gentamicin and chloramphenicol, while remaining susceptible to ciprofloxacin and amikacin.

This theory backed up the research done by (Mooney and Gamelli,1989), who noted that "burn wound infections are among the most significant and dangerous complications that arise in the immediate aftermath of an injury". The type and amount of microorganisms as well as the injured tissue play a role in the healing

process, and these complications represent major causes of morbidity and mortality. Hospital burn units are highly contaminated, as shown by the fact that the majority of germs were combined with other bacterial species and some of them were resistant to antibiotics.

This higher frequency may be brought on by variables such as the use of antibiotics, immunosuppressive burn trauma effects, or the acquisition of nosocomial bacteria in patients requiring extended hospital stays. These findings supported what several workers had previously seen. To maintain homeostasis and return physiology to normal, when there is extensive burn injury, the immune system responds by becoming pro-inflammatory initially and mostly anti-inflammatory later on. This transition is mediated by both the cellular response and cytokines (Chaudry and Ayala (1993).

Pro-inflammatory cytokines trigger the systemic responses to burn injury (Gamelli et al., (1994), while anti-inflammatory responses & subsequent immunosuppression post-burn wound are a complex combination of cells and cytokines at odds; there is a decrease in production and release of monocytes and macrophages after burn and sepsis (Embil et al., 2001). Additionally, *Embile et al.*, 2001 noted that microorganisms were nosocomially transferred to the burn wound through contact with medical personnel and immersion hydrotherapy treatment. Their findings on the isolation of bacteria from burn wounds agreed with those of other earlier investigations. *Pseudomonas* species was the most often isolated pathogen from burn wounds (51.5%), according to (Mehta et al., 2007).

A. baumannii (14.28%), *S. aureus* (11.15%), *Klebsiella* spp. (9.23%), and *Proteus* spp. (2.3%) were next most common organisms isolated. *P. aeruginosa* was the most commonly isolated pathogen accounting for 59% of isolates, followed by *Staphylococcus aureus* at 17.5%, *Acinetobacter* species at 7.2%, *Klebsiella* species at 3.9%, *Enterobacter* at 3.9%, *Proteus* species at 3.3%, and a few other pathogens at 4.8% Agnihotri et al., 2004). This is similar to the information from Agnihotri et al., 1999.

According to (Arslan et al. 1999), *P. aeruginosa* is the most common kind of bacteria found in burn wounds in Adana, Turkey, accounting for 53% of cases. The subsequent organisms in the sequence are "*P. mirabilis* (10%), *Acinetobacter spp.* (7%), *K. pneumonia* (7%), and *E. coli* (3%)".

One of the most typical and severe risks in patients with open wounds is the presence of microbial infections. It is evident that *P. aeruginosa* was cultured from 22 (48.9%) of burn wound swabs in the current study and confirms its etiological role in wound infection. Within the setting studied, *P. aeruginosa* was isolated from 10% and 13% burn wound infections in published papers reported by (Al-hadithi, 2007). and (Mahmoud 2009). The results of the study showed that the rate of isolation of gram-negative organisms was much greater than that of gram-positive organisms. The results were in alignment with the findings published by (Kehinde et al., 2004). who had noted that Gram-negative bacteria were isolated from burn sites at a rate that was more than twice as high as gram-positive bacteria, with *Klebsiella spp.* making up the largest proportion of isolates (34.4% of all isolates) followed by *P. aeruginosa* in percent (29%) & *S. aureus* in percent (26.8%). Many of the isolates were resistant to multiple antibiotics.

Conclusion

It is concluded from this research as well as other researches that burn wound infections still pose a threat to human life along with increasing antibiotic resistance which requires the attention of preventive and control measures.

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